

Molecular and crystalline architectures of a luminous dinuclear cadmium(II) dicyanamide compound containing a tetradentate Schiff base as an end-capping ligand

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Abstract : The dinuclear complex $[\text{Cd}(\text{L})(\mu_{1,5}\text{-dca})_2(\text{PF}_6)_2 \cdot \text{MeOH}$ (**1**) [$\text{L} = N,N'$ -(bis(pyridine-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,3-propanediamine; dca = dicyanamide] has been isolated following an earlier procedure and structure is determined by X-ray diffraction measurement. Structural analysis shows that each cadmium(II) center in **1** is located in a distorted octahedral environment coordinated by the four N atoms of L and two nitrile N atoms of bridged $\mu_{1,5}$ -dca units. Individual dinuclear units of **1** are associated by $\pi \cdots \pi$ and C-H \cdots π interactions resulting in a 2D sheet structure which is further strengthened by multiple C-H \cdots F and C-H \cdots N hydrogen bonds. **1** displays high-energy intraligand $^1(\pi\text{-}\pi^*)$ fluorescence in DMF solution at room temperature.

Keywords : Dinuclear cadmium(II), Schiff base, dicyanamide bridge, X-ray structure, fluorescence.

Introduction

The study of mono-, di-, and polynuclear complexes of cadmium(II) is of intense current interest in search of functional materials¹⁻⁴ specially with electronic² and optoelectronic³ properties. One-pot synthesis⁵ using appropriate mole ratios of metal ions, organic ligands and bridging units may afford various molecular and crystalline architectures⁶. Pseudohalides⁷ are versatile bridging ligands; of them larger-sized molecular ion rod, dicyanamide (dca)⁸, is gaining recent interest due to its versatile coordination motifs. Different research groups have explored⁸⁻¹⁰ dca chemistry with different transition and non-transition metal ions in combination with polyamines, polyimines, macrocycles, etc. of varied denticities. The corresponding chemistry of dca with Schiff base ligands is scarce. Schiff bases^{11,12} have recently been focused by the coordination chemists because of their preparative accessibilities, structural varieties, and varied denticities. Recently, we are active¹³⁻¹⁵ to prepare dca complexes of different 3d and 4d metal ions in combination with Schiff bases towards characterization of new magnetic and luminous materials. The variation of molar ratios of metal ions, blocking ligands, bridging units and

counter ions leads to varied molecular and crystalline architectures with tunable properties. We reported¹³ the structure and properties of the compound $[\text{Cd}(\text{L})(\mu_{1,5}\text{-dca})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 0.66(\text{CH}_3\text{OH})$ [$\text{L} = N,N'$ -(bis(pyridine-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,3-propane-diamine]. To establish the effect of counter anions on molecular as well as crystalline architecture, herein we report a new cadmium(II)-dca complex of the composition $[\text{Cd}(\text{L})(\mu_{1,5}\text{-dca})_2(\text{PF}_6)_2 \cdot \text{MeOH}$ (**1**). The details of isolation, characterization, molecular and crystalline architectures, and luminous behaviour are described below.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

The isolation of **1** can be achieved in high yield by the reaction of 1 : 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of cadmium(II) acetate, L, dca and NH_4PF_6 in methanolic solution at room temperature. The metal ion and Schiff base are used in 1 : 1 molar ratio so that four coordination sites around each six coordinated cadmium(II) could be completed by two dicyanamide ions through its bridging mode. The procedure is summarized in eq. (1).

The complex was characterized by elemental analyses, spectroscopic studies and other physicochemical results. The microanalytical data are in good conformity with formulation **1**. The compound is air-stable and moisture-insensitive, and is soluble in common organic solvents such as methanol, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide, but is insoluble in water. In MeCN solution, it shows conductivity value [$\Lambda_M = 232 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$] corresponding to a 2 : 1 electrolytic behavior¹⁶.

Spectroscopic study :

In IR, the stretching vibrations of dca in **1** are seen as strong $\nu_s(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ absorptions in the region 2170–2190 cm^{-1} (2183 cm^{-1}) and two weak to medium $\nu_{\text{as}} + \nu_s(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ and $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ absorptions in the range 2240–2310 cm^{-1} (2301, 2235 cm^{-1}); the shift towards higher frequency values as compared to those of free dca (2286, 2232 and 2179 cm^{-1})¹⁷ is presumably due to bibringing $\mu_{1,5}$ coordination mode of the pseudohalide¹⁸. Bands corresponding to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C}-\text{N})$ and $\nu_s(\text{C}-\text{N})$ stretching vibrations of dca are found at 1357, 1319 cm^{-1} and at 926 cm^{-1} , respectively. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ plus $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ stretching frequencies¹⁹ of the metal-bound Schiff base (L) are observed at 1624 and 1593 cm^{-1} , respectively. The hexafluorophosphate bands¹⁹ are observed at 843 and 558 cm^{-1} .

Luminescence property :

In DMF solutions, free Schiff base (L) shows absorption maximum at 271 nm and the corresponding cadmium(II) compound **1** exhibits band at 280 nm assignable to ligand-based charge transfer²⁰. Upon photo-excitation at the corresponding absorption bands, L exhibits a broad fluorescent emission centered at 383 nm; whereas **1** shows albeit red-shifted and more intense emission centered at 387 nm. The characteristic spectral behaviours of free L and the compound **1** are shown in Fig. 1. The luminescence behaviour^{21,22} in **1** may be attributed to the intraligand $^1(\pi-\pi^*)$ transition and the red shift as well as greater intensity may presumably be due to the increase in conformational rigidity of L upon coordination.

Fig. 1. Fluorescence spectra of L and **1** in DMF solutions at 298 K.

Crystal structure :

In order to define the coordination sphere conclusively, single-crystal X-ray diffraction study of **1** was made. An ORTEP diagram with atom numbering scheme of the cation in **1** is shown in Fig. 2. Selected interatomic bond lengths and bond angles are listed in Table 1, and significant non-covalent interaction parameters are set in Table 2. The structure is made up of a centrosymmetric dicationic dinuclear unit $[\text{Cd(L)}(\mu_{1,5}\text{-dca})]_2^{2+}$, PF_6^- counter anions and disordered CH_3OH molecules. On application of symmetry operations CH_3OH molecule appears as three atoms which are equal to one molecule of CH_3OH per dinuclear unit with O1 atom in the inversion center. It is worth mentioning that the asymmetric unit of the reported perchlorate analogue¹³ contains two different dinuclear $[\text{Cd(L)}(\mu_{1,5}\text{-dca})]_2^{2+}$ moieties of which one is centrosymmetric (Cd1 and Cd1a) and the other has two crystallographically independent cadmium(II) centers (Cd2 and Cd3). Within the complex cation of **1** the two cadmium(II) centers (Cd1 and Cd1b; $b = 1-x, 2-y, 1-z$) are bridged by two $\mu_{1,5}$ -dca to form a 12-membered $\text{Cd}(\text{NCNCN})_2\text{-Cd}$ ring with boat conformation. The overall geometry around each cadmium(II) is best described as a distorted octahedron with a CdN_6 chromophore. Two imine N (N1 and N4), one pyridine N (N3) and one nitrile N (N5) atom of one $\mu_{1,5}$ -dca unit constitute the equatorial plane whereas one remaining pyridine N (N2) and nitrile N (N6) atoms occupy the two axial positions around each

Fig. 2. ORTEP diagram of $[\text{Cd}(\text{L})(\mu_{1,5}\text{-dca})]_2^{2+}$ in **1** with atom labeling scheme and 50% probability ellipsoids for all non-hydrogen atoms (symmetry code : $b = 1-x, 2-y, 1+z$).

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for **1**

Bond distances					
Cd1-N6	2.293(9)	Cd1-N3	2.325(7)	Cd1-N5	2.332(10)
Cd1-N1	2.330(7)	Cd1-N2	2.343(7)	Cd1-N4	2.358(7)
N5-C25	1.133(11)	N6-C26 ^b	1.132(12)		
Bond angles					
N6-Cd1-N3	111.8(3)	N6-Cd1-N5	82.7(3)	N3-Cd1-N5	89.5(3)
N6-Cd1-N1	97.6(3)	N3-Cd1-N1	135.4(2)	N1-Cd1-N5	128.2(3)
N6-Cd1-N2	145.4(3)	N3-Cd1-N2	98.6(3)	N5-Cd1-N2	81.3(3)
N1-Cd1-N2	69.5(3)	N6-Cd1-N4	83.9(3)	N3-Cd1-N4	70.3(3)
N5-Cd1-N4	149.5(3)	N1-Cd1-N4	80.7(3)	N2-Cd1-N4	123.2(2)
C11-N4-Cd1	117.9(6)	C28-N4-Cd1	120.9(6)	C25-N5-Cd1	152.7(9)
C26 ^b -N6-Cd1	151.9(9)	N6 ^b -C26-N7	174.1(11)	N5-C25-N7	73.9(10)

Symmetry code : $b = 1-x, 2-y, 1-z$.

Table 2. Hydrogen bond and C-H... π interaction parameters (Å, °) for **1**

D-H...A	D-H	H...A	D...A	D-H...A
C5-H5...F3 ⁱ	0.93	2.51	3.284(15)	141
C19-H19...F1 ⁱ	0.93	2.51	3.201(13)	131
C31-H31A...N2 ⁱⁱ	0.96	2.33	3.20(2)	151
C31-H31C...F2 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.96	2.10	2.75(3)	123
C(23)-H(23)...Cg(5) ^{iv}	0.93	2.90	3.740(14)	152
π ... π interaction for 1				
Cg(i)→Cg(j)	Dihedral angle (i,j) (°)	Centroid separation Cg-Cg (Å)	Vertical displacement of Cg's (Å)	Slippage (Å)
Cg4→Cg4 ⁱ	0	3.737(5)	3.410(4)	1.536

Symmetry code : $i = 1-x, 2-y, 2-z$; $ii = 1-x, 1-y, 1-z$; $iii = -x, 1-y, 1-z$; $iv = 2-x, 2-y, 1-z$;
 Cg4 = N(2)-C(1)-C(2)-C(3)-C(4)-C(5); Cg5 = N(3)-C(16)-C(17)-C(27)-C(19)-C(18)

cadmium(II) center. Among four basal N atoms, N5/N5b and N4/N4b deviate 0.310 and 0.555 Å, respectively from the equatorial plane towards the axial nitrile N (N6/N6b) atom whereas N1/N1b and N3/N3b depart 0.337 and 0.528 Å, respectively towards the axial pyridine N (N2/N2b) atom from the mean plane. The cadmium(II) center (Cd1/Cd1b) lies almost in the mean plane (deviation : 0.107 Å). Cd-N bond distances lie in the range 2.293(10)–2.360(8) Å (Table 1). The tetradentate ligand is twisted around the cadmium(II) center such that the two planes containing the unsaturated chelate rings (Cd1, N1, C6, C1, N2) and (Cd1, N3, C16, C11, N4) are inclined at 63.328(19)° to each other. The degrees of distortion from ideal octahedral geometry are reflected in *cisoid* [80.9(3)–128.2(3)°] and *transoid* [149.3(3)–135.4(3)°] bond angles; the N5-Cd1-N6 bridging angle is 82.6(3)°. In Cd-(NCNCN)₂-Cd linkage, the dca units do not coordinate to the metal centers in a perfectly linear arrangement, as is reflected in the bond angles of Cd1-N5-C25 152.7(9)° and Cd1-N6-C26b 152.1(9)°. The intradinuclear Cd...Cd distance (7.833 Å) in **1** is slightly shorter than that (7.904 and 7.879 Å) in the reported perchlorate analogue¹³.

In the crystalline state, the 0D dinuclear units of **1** are packed with each other into a 2D sheet parallel to *ac*-plane (Fig. 3) through edge-to-face C–H... π and face-to-face π ... π interactions (Table 2). This is in contrast to

that of the perchlorate analogue¹³ where multiple C–H...O and C–H...N hydrogen bonds result in a 2D sheet parallel to *ab*-plane. The 2D sheet of **1** is further stabilized by multiple C–H...F and C–H...N hydrogen bonds (Table 2) involving the H atoms of the ligand framework and the disordered solvent molecule, F atom of the interstitial PF₆[−] counter anion and imine N of the ligand backbone while the 2D sheet of the perchlorate analogue¹³ is further stabilized by O–H...O hydrogen bond involving the H atom of the solvent molecule and O atom of the interstitial ClO₄[−] counter anion in combination with π ... π interactions.

Conclusion :

One new luminous dinuclear cadmium(II) dicyanamide complex in combination with a tetradentate Schiff base (L) is isolated and X-ray crystallographically characterized. This work reflects substantial effect of counter ions on the molecular and crystalline architectures and thereby the related properties.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity 2-benzoylpyridine (Lancaster, UK), 1,3-propanediamine (Spectrochem, India), cadmium(II) acetate (SRL, India), sodium dicyanamide (Lancaster, UK) and ammonium hexafluorophosphate (Fluka, Germany) were

Fig. 3. A perspective view of 2D sheet structure in **1** parallel to *ac*-plane formed by cooperative π ... π and C–H... π interactions along with further stabilization of the 2D sheet through multiple C–H...F and C–H...N hydrogen bonds.

purchased from respective concerns and used as received. The Schiff base, *N,N'*-(bis(pyridin-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,3-propanediamine (L) belonging to symmetrical N^P , N^i , N^i , N^P type backbone, [$N^P = N(\text{pyridine})$ and $N^i = N(\text{imine})$] was prepared by condensation of 1 : 2 molar ratio of 1,3-propanediamine and 2-benzoylpyridine following a reported method¹³. All other chemicals and solvents used were AR grade. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air.

Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were done using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–400 cm^{-1}) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer. Molar conductances were measured using a Systronics conductivity meter where the cell constant was calibrated with 0.01 *M* KCl solution and dry MeCN was used as solvent. Thermal behaviors were investigated with a Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DT analyzer heated from 30–750 °C under nitrogen. UV-Vis (in DMF) was measured with a Jasco model V-570 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer. Fluorescence measurements were done using Hitachi fluorescence spectrofluorimeter F-4500.

Preparation of the complex :

$[\text{Cd}(\text{L})(\mu_{1,5}\text{-dca})]_2(\text{PF}_6)_2 \cdot \text{MeOH}$ (**1**) : A methanolic solution (10 ml) of L (405 mg, 1 mmol) was added slowly to a solution (20 ml) of $\text{Cd}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (266 mg, 1 mmol) in the same solvent followed by the addition of methanolic solutions (10 ml each) of Na(dca) (89 mg, 1 mmol) and NH_4PF_6 (163 mg, 1 mmol) in succession. The final light yellow solution was left undisturbed in air for slow evaporation. After a few days colourless single crystals of **1** that separated, were washed with hexane and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield : 546 mg (75%). Found : C, 47.7; H, 3.7; N, 13.3. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{59}\text{H}_{52}\text{N}_{14}\text{OF}_{12}\text{P}_2\text{Cd}_2$ (**1**) : C, 47.6; H, 3.5; N, 13.2%. IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu_{\text{as}} + \nu_{\text{s}}(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ 2301; $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ 2235; $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ 2183; $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C}-\text{N})$ 1357, 1319; $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{C}-\text{N})$ 926; $\nu(\text{PF}_6)$ 843, 558. UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm in DMF) : 280.

X-Ray crystallographic analysis :

Diffraction data of the single crystals of **1** was collected at 293(2) K on a Bruker SMART APEX II CCD area-detector diffractometer using graphite monochromated Mo-K α radiation (0.71073 Å). For unit cell determination, the single crystal was exposed to X-rays for 10 s in

three sets of frames. The detector frames were integrated by using SAINT²³. The empirical absorption correction was performed using SADABS program²⁴. The best single crystal of **1** selected for data collection gave diffuse diffraction spots were overlapping and the integration of these spots could not be carried out properly by the processing software. Consequently, a small portion of the reflections collected was rejected and the structure was refined using the available data ($1.81^\circ \leq \theta \leq 19.54^\circ$), which was adequate to give a precise structure. The structure was solved by direct methods using SHELXS-97²⁵ and refined by SHELXL-97²⁶. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters whereas hydrogen atoms were placed in calculated positions and refined using a standard riding model. All calculations were carried out using SHELXTL²⁷ and Mercury 1.4²⁸ programs. Further details are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Crystallographic data for $[\text{Cd}(\text{L})(\mu_{1,5}\text{-dca})]_2(\text{PF}_6)_2 \cdot \text{MeOH}$ (**1**)

Crystal parameters	1
CCDC No.	870214
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{59}\text{H}_{52}\text{N}_{14}\text{OF}_{12}\text{P}_2\text{Cd}_2$
Formula weight	1488.04
Temperature (K)	293(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	P-1
<i>a</i> (Å)	10.947(2)
<i>b</i> (Å)	12.5815(12)
<i>c</i> (Å)	12.8318(11)
α (°)	117.567(2)
β (°)	94.416(3)
γ (°)	95.877(3)
Crystal size (mm^3)	0.21 × 0.17 × 0.08
Volume (Å ³)	1542.8(4)
<i>Z</i>	1
Calculated density (g cm^{-3})	1.617
Absorption coefficient (mm^{-1})	0.832
<i>F</i> (000)	754
θ range for data collection (°)	1.81 to 19.54
Limiting indices	-10 < = <i>h</i> < = 10, -11 < = <i>k</i> < = 11, -12 < = <i>l</i> < = 12
<i>T</i> _{min} and <i>T</i> _{max}	0.85 and 0.94
Reflections collected/unique	8558/2686

Table-3 (contd.)

Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2
Data/restraints/parameters	2686/6/413
R_{int}	0.068
Final R_1 values ($I > 2\sigma(I)$)	0.0424
Final $wR(F^2)$ values ($I > 2\sigma(I)$)	0.0953
Final R_1 values (all data)	0.0655
Final $wR(F^2)$ values (all data)	0.1065
Goodness of fit on F^2	1.054
Largest peak and hole ($\text{e}\text{\AA}^{-3}$)	0.312 and -0.501
Weighting scheme : $R_1 = \Sigma F_o - F_c / \Sigma F_o $, $wR = [\Sigma w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / \Sigma w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}$, Calcd. $w = 1 / [\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (0.0479P)^2 + 1.3522P]$ (1); where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2) / 3$.	

Supplementary data :

Crystallographic data (excluding structure factors) for **1** has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre No. CCDC 870214. Copies of this information can be obtained, free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : +44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

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